

A1404

Physics-Constrained Bayesian Optimization of a GRU-based black-box function to optimize the operating conditions of a Proton Exchange Membrane fuel cell

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Abstract

Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC) are a promising solution in the energy transition focused on reducing CO₂ and utilizing renewable energies. As part of the development of these components, enhancing both performance and durability is crucial as they are expected to achieve longer lifespans. This research develops an optimization framework to optimize operational parameters within the constraints of physical laws, thus maximizing PEMFC performance in high-power applications. The study involves the analysis of over 500 hours of experimental data, leading to the creation of a surrogate model for the FC using Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), which serves as a black-box function. These functions do not possess an analytical expression, lack derivatives and require computational-costly evaluations. Therefore, Bayesian Optimization (BO) is adopted as a solver for physics-constrained optimization, given its demonstrated effectiveness in optimizing black-box functions. The findings reveal that a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) surrogate shows high precision and reliability as a model, achieving an accuracy of over 98% in replicating the FC's internal state regarding physical parameters. When integrated with the optimization framework, it identifies optimal parameter combinations within the feasible region defined by the physics constraints, leading to an improvement in FC performance up to 5 %.

Figure 1: Illustration of the optimization framework.

Introduction

State-of-the-art analytical equations often struggle to accurately capture fuel cell behavior under dynamic loads and varying conditions. Data-driven models are gaining traction in predictive engineering applications, including Support Vector Regressors (SVRs) [1], Random Forests (RF) [2], and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) [3]. For instance, Liu et al. [4] used a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) model for PEM fuel cell durability estimation, achieving an R² score [24] of 95.5%. Echabbarri et al. [5] presented a model leveraging kernel principal component analysis and XGBRegressor, optimized via Bayesian methods, outperforming traditional approaches by 6.35%, 6.8%, and 4.8% over ANN, SVR, and XGBRegressor. Wilberforce et al. [6] combined convolutional and bi-recurrent neural networks to predict the remaining useful life of PEM fuel cells, attaining a relative error of 0.12, compared to 2.61 in LSTM models. The challenge is integrating these models into optimization frameworks, given that classical methods operate on analytically defined problems [7]. Solutions to black box or derivative-free models employ methods like Direct Search [8], Metaheuristics and Global Optimizers [7]. Zhou et al. [9] enhanced fuel cell efficiency by optimizing operational parameters using simulations, experiments, machine learning, and Genetic Algorithms (GA), achieving a 6% rise in net output power with efficiency over 55%. Sun et al. [10] created a multi-objective optimization (MOO) framework using GAs and a six-hidden-layer Deep Neural Network (DNN) to optimize renewable energy for Solid Oxide fuel cells (SOFCs).

Lu et al. [11] explored machine learning-based Bayesian Optimization (BO) to improve ultrafiltration processes, utilizing XGBoost to identify optimal parameters, achieving steady flux with less than 0.5% error. However, employing BO with black-box models can yield infeasible solutions contradicting physical laws, especially in fuel cell thermal and electrochemical principles. Sattari et al. [12] developed a MOO-BO framework with physics-informed constraints, optimizing a thermoplastics 3D printer. Their approach raised the percentage of samples meeting performance standards from 65% to 83%, achieving five Pareto frontier points within 36 iterations. Similarly to this approach, the innovative feature of this study is the integration of a physical thermal model expressed in analytical form as a constraint, which ensures that the optimizer identifies feasible solutions that adhere to these fundamental principles.

1. Experiments

Multiple campaigns have been conducted on a test bench, accumulating a total of 500 operational hours. Each test bench is equipped with experimental fuel cell modules, consisting of a stack of 5 cells designed for a nominal output power of 1 kW. The primary goal of these modules is to assess system performance under varying operating conditions, which are influenced by four main categories of input parameters: electrical, fluidic, thermal, and control inputs. For a simplified diagram of the test benches, refer to Fig. 1. The H₂, Air, and N₂ supply lines deliver pressurized gases to the test benches, with pressure regulators enabling adjustment of the desired inlet pressure. Additionally, water for gas humidification is regularly supplied by an operator using a container beneath the bench. This water is pumped into a pressurized stainless-steel pot, which then provides the channels with water for stack humidification.

Figure 1: Simplified diagram of the fuel cell stack components [23].

During the experiments, a Design of Experiments (DOE) was conducted, with the aim to characterize fuel cell stack performance within a 7-dimensional operational space (θ): Stack Temperature, Cathode pressure inlet, Cathode Relative Humidity, Anode Relative Humidity, Cathode λ , Anode λ , Current Density, where λ represents the stoichiometric coefficient. This mapping will identify influential factors on performance, control degrees of freedom, and support model calibration. Each parameter combination in the DOE follows protocols:

1. Polarization Curve (CPL) to extract stabilized voltages at various current levels.
2. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) performed at select current levels of the polarization curve, with up to 14 EIS tests conducted per curve.

A total of 60 different combinations of input parameters (θ) were tested in the variables' space shown Table 1. The modules were subjected to a simulated high-power load for 7-hour operational cycles. After each cycle, an extensive stop was enforced for effective purging of inert gases and water. During each cycle, the reference combination and two distinct combinations of θ were tested, with polarization curves plotted at both the start and end to monitor degradation, along with two curves extracted for each θ combination.

Table 1: Explored space for each physical parameter.

Parameter	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Temperature _{stack} [°C]	35	85
Pressure _{inlet,air} [mbara]	1.3	2.5
RH _{inlet,air} [%]	20	80
RH _{inlet,H2} [%]	20	80
Stochio _{air} [-]	1.5	3.5
Stochio _{n2} [-]	1.1	1.5
J _{setpoint} [A/cm ²]	0	1.5

2. Methodology

Surrogate model: Gated Recurrent Units neural networks

Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) are a type of neural network that belongs to the family of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). These networks have demonstrated exceptional capabilities in time-series prediction tasks by effectively considering the influence of past events on future forecasts. In our study, the selected architecture serves as a surrogate model that can accurately replicate the output performance of the fuel cell under various operating conditions. This model is designed to account for the impact of previous states, determined by operating conditions, on future states. The implementation of the algorithm utilizes the API resources available in PyTorch [13]. The GRU cell is characterized by three gates: the reset gate R_t , the update gate Z_t , and the candidate hidden state gate \tilde{H}_t . The mathematical explanations can be derived from the manual "Dive into Deep Learning" by Zhang et al. [14]. This architecture is used to create a surrogate model that acts as black box functions in the optimization process. The experimental dataset was divided into three parts: 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing the model. The validation set

is used specifically for hyperparameter tuning, which encompasses factors such as the number of hidden layers, the number of neurons per layer, learning rate, beta, number of epochs, and dropout rate. The chosen optimizer for this task is the Adam optimizer. Table 2 summarizes the final hyperparameters selected for model evaluation. The models' performance was evaluated using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to calculate the loss function, while both the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and RMSE to compare actual values against predicted values.

Table 2: Hyperparameters tested of the GRU model.

Hyperparameter	Values tested	Best
Learning Rate	0.1, 0.01, 0.001	0.01
Epochs	100, 200, 500, 1000	500
Number of layers	1,2,3,4	3
Dropout rate	0, 0.3, 0.5	0.3
Sequence length	10, 30, 60	10
Batch size	32, 64, 128	128

Physics-constrained Optimization

The core description of the problem is encapsulated in Equation 1, where the objective function seeks to maximize the performance of the stack. This is articulated through Surrogate Model 1 (SM1) and Surrogate Model 2 (SM2), which function as black box representations of voltage behavior based on a set of input parameters θ . The inequality constraint G1 defines the feasible region for optimization. Furthermore, X_L and X_U represent the lower and upper bounds for each variable associated with the elements of θ . The decision to develop two distinct surrogate models is driven by the need to ensure that the initial output from SM1, which represents the system's physical state, conforms to the constraints set by the theoretical framework of PEMFCs.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{max} &= f(SM_1, SM_2) : \text{Objective function} && \text{eq. 1} \\
 G_1(SM_1, SM_2) &< \epsilon_1 : \text{Inequality Constraint} \\
 s. t: & \text{Lowerbound} \leq \theta_i \leq \text{Upperbound} : \text{Variable Space}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where: $\theta = [T_{stack, set}, P_{set, inlet, anode}, P_{set, inlet, cathode}, RH_{set, inlet, anode}, RH_{set, inlet, cathode}, RelHum_{set, inlet, cathode}, Stochio_{set, anode}, Stochio_{set, cathode}]$

Objective function

SM1 is trained using the elements of θ as input features of the model. Its output reflects the current state of the system by returning the inlet and outlet conditions of the primary physical parameters. SM2 takes as input the outputs generated by the first model and predicts the stack voltage. The features and targets for both surrogate models, SM1 and SM2, are summarized in Table 3. The optimization aims to maximize the stack voltage of the fuel cell by identifying the optimal values of the control inputs θ as functions of different power outputs demanded. Our optimization approach looks at each operational region, which includes activation (current density ranges between 0 and 0.2), ohmic (current density ranges between 0.2 and 1), and concentration (current density is greater than 1), therefore maximizing the mean integral under the curve obtained for each one (Eq. 2).

$$f_{max} = \frac{1}{J_{max, region_i} - J_{min, region_i}} \int_J V_{stack} dJ \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

Table 3: Features and target variables for SM1 and SM2

SM1 Features	SM1 Targets	SM2 Features	SM2 Target
$Temperature_{stack, setpoint}$	$Temperature_{inlet, air}$; $Temperature_{outlet, air}$ $Temperature_{inlet, H2}$; $Temperature_{outlet, H2}$ $Temperature_{inlet, coolant}$; $Temperature_{outlet, coolant}$		$Voltage_{stack}$
$Pressure_{inlet, air, setpoint}$	$Pressure_{inlet, air}$; $Pressure_{outlet, air}$ $Pressure_{inlet, H2}$; $Pressure_{outlet, H2}$		
$RH_{inlet, air, setpoint}$	$RH_{inlet, air}$ $RH_{inlet, H2}$		
$RH_{inlet, H2, setpoint}$	$Flowrate_{air}$ $Flowrate_{H2}$		
$Stochio_{air, setpoint}$		$J_{setpoint}$	
$Stochio_{H2, setpoint}$			
$J_{setpoint}$			

Constraints

The inequality constraints determine the feasible region for potential solution sets based on the key principles of fuel cells' theory. In this study, the constraint equation (Eq. 3) illustrates the balance of thermal power. The derivation of this formula is obtained under the following hypotheses:

- The amount of water transferred from the cathode to the anode, caused by the pressure, temperature, and species concentration gradients between the cathode and the anode compartment, is experimentally measured by comparing the amount of water recovered at the outlet of each compartment.
- The mean stack temperature is assumed to be equivalent to the outlet coolant temperature.
- The relative humidity is near saturation or quasi-saturation under outlet conditions. The difference in water vapor content between the inlet and outlet allows for the calculation of the water that either condenses or evaporates, and consequently, the associated latent heat.
- Thermal losses between the stack and the ambient environment are neglected, as their impact is minimal due to the controlled operating conditions within the test laboratory.
- In experimental bench tests involving a small number of cells, operating the system at low current levels may lead to a reversal of heat transfer—from the coolant to the stack—due to the action of thermal regulation.

$$Q_{coolant} = Q_{th,react,HHV} - P_{elec} - \sum Q_{sens} - \sum Q_{lat} - \sum Q_{loss} \quad eq. 3$$

Being $Q_{coolant}$ the heat extracted by the coolant, $Q_{th,react,HHV}$ the heat power released during the reaction considering its higher heating value (HHV) [15], and P_{elec} the electrical work produced by the stack, as well as Q_{sens} and Q_{lat} representing the sensible and latent heat carried by the reactants entering the fuel cell.

$$Q_{coolant} = m_{coolant} \cdot Cp_{coolant} \cdot (T_{coolant,outlet} - T_{coolant,inlet}) \quad eq. 4$$

$$Q_{th,reaction,HHV} = \frac{U_{HHV}}{2F} \cdot I \cdot N_{cells} = 1.482 \cdot I \cdot N_{cells} \quad eq. 5$$

$$P_{elec} = U_{stack} \cdot I \quad eq. 6$$

$$Q_{sens,reactant} = (\dot{n} Cp_{T_{out}})_{reactant,in} + (\dot{n} Cp_{T_{out}})_{vap,in} \cdot (T_{out,stack} - T_{in,reactant}) \quad eq. 7$$

$$Q_{latent,reactant} = \dot{n}_{cond-vap} \cdot L_{@T_{out}} \quad eq. 8$$

$$Q_{loss} = Q_{convection} + Q_{radiation} \quad eq. 9$$

Let $m_{coolant}$ represent the mass flow rate of the coolant, C_p the specific heat, I the current of the stack, N_{cells} the number of cells in the stack module, F the Faraday constant, and \dot{n} the molar flow rate of the reactants (H₂ and air). L denotes the latent heat, calculated at the outlet temperature of the stack for each reactant. The term Q_{loss} represents the dissipated heat to the external ambient, determined by convection and radiation exchange. As mentioned before, this term is neglected in this study. By taking Eq. 4, Eq. 5, Eq. 6, Eq. 7 Eq. 8 and substituting into Eq. 3, the inequality constraint is obtained (Eq. 10), where ϵ corresponds to the average RMSE obtained during the validation of the model on the experimental data (further details can be found in the results section). The terms in the equations are substituted by the output of SM1 and SM2.

$$G(SM1, SM2) = Q_{coolant} - (Q_{th, reaction, HHV} - P_{elec} - \sum Q_{sensible} - \sum Q_{latent}) \leq \epsilon \quad eq. 10$$

Bayesian Optimization

Paulson and Tsay [16] highlight the two main components in BO methods: (a) a predictive surrogate model equipped with uncertainty estimates (typically described by Bayesian statistics) and (b) an acquisition function (AF) whose value at any point $x \in X$ dictates the exploration policy of the optimizer given existing observations D_k . Gaussian processes (GPs) are the most used surrogate models in BO due to their ability to analytically propagate uncertainty and their nonparametric nature. Assuming the common setting of a single output (or a single output per GP), we let $f^k(x) \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\Sigma^k(x) \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times m}$ denote the surrogate mean and covariance predictors for $f(x)$ given data D_k . These quantities can be used to construct an uncertainty set $F_k(x)$. For example, for a multivariate normal distribution, one can select an α -level confidence region:

$$F_k(x) = \{y \in \mathbb{R}: (y - \hat{f}_k(x))^T \widehat{\Sigma}_k^{-1}(x) (y - \hat{f}_k(x)) \leq r(\alpha)\} \quad eq. 11$$

where $r(\alpha)$ is the radius of the ellipsoid that corresponds to the cumulative χ^2 distribution with χ^2 degrees of freedom evaluated at confidence level ($\alpha \in (0,1)$). The choice of predictive model is a very important component of BO, as performance relies on the quality of the model used to select sample locations. Given a surrogate model $\hat{f}_k(x)$ and $\hat{\Sigma}_k(x)$ we must then select a particular AF ($\alpha_k: X \rightarrow R$) where the subscript (k) highlights its dependence on (D_k). The BO sampling policy can then be formally written as: $x_{k+1} \in \arg \max x \in X \alpha_k(x)$. One can map the choice of AF to that of a reward function $R(D_k)$. Specifically, we can think of (α_k) as the one-step expected increase in reward: $\alpha_k(x) = Ek[R(D_k \cup x, yx) - R(D_k)]$ where (Ek) refers to the expectation under the posterior distribution given (D_k). In this study, the AF used is the upper confidence bound (UCB) acquisition function: it is one of the simplest forms of acquisition functions, incorporating explicit terms for exploitation $\mu(x)$ and exploration $\sigma(x)$:

$$\alpha_k(x; \lambda) = \mu(x) + \lambda \sigma(x) \quad eq. 12$$

With UCB, the tradeoff between exploitation and exploration is straightforward and controlled by the parameter λ . Concretely, UCB is a weighted sum of the expected performance, captured by the GP's mean $\mu(x)$, and the uncertainty, represented by the standard deviation $\sigma(x)$ When λ is small, BO prioritizes solutions expected to perform well, i.e., those with high $\mu(x)$. Instead, when λ is large, BO emphasizes exploration, encouraging

sampling in less-charted regions of the search space [17][18]. The algorithm is implemented using the Bayesian Optimization library for Python [19].

3. Results

Validation of surrogate models 1 and 2

SM1 is designed to predict the internal state of the fuel cell based on the control inputs (the set of input parameters θ). Fig. 2 illustrates the prediction results of SM1 for each variable across the test set. The data in this figure is sorted in ascending order, enabling a straightforward assessment of the model's capacity to predict values with comparable performances across the entire value space. The average MAPE score is 1.3 percent, while the average RMSE stands at 0.73. SM2 takes the internal state predicted by SM1 as input features to forecast the FC voltage as output. The model achieved a MAPE score of 0.76% on the train set, while 0.83% on the test set. To demonstrate the quality of the model, it has been compared with two other approaches: a traditional machine learning model, specifically the SVR with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel [20], as previously mentioned in the introduction of this paper (section 1), and an electrochemical model proposed by Espinosa-López [21] in analytical form (Eq. 17). This electrochemical model is expressed as a function of current density, temperature, and pressure, and can be divided into four distinct terms [22]: open circuit voltage (OCV) at Nernst Equilibrium, activation loss, ohmic loss, and concentration loss. The results (Fig. 3) indicate that the GRU model outperforms both other models, particularly at high current levels, which corresponds to the diffusion term and is challenging to represent in analytical form.

$$u_{nernst} = 1.23 - 0.0009 \cdot (T - T_{std}) + \left(\frac{R \cdot T}{2 \cdot F}\right) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{p_{H_2} \cdot p_{O_2}^{0.5}}{p_{H_2O}}\right) \quad eq.13$$

$$Act_{loss} = A \cdot \ln\left(\frac{i + i_{corr}}{i_0}\right) \quad eq.14$$

$$Ohm_{loss} = r \cdot (i + i_{corr}) \quad eq.15$$

$$Conc_{loss} = -B \cdot \ln\left(1 - \frac{i + i_{corr}}{i_{lim}}\right) \quad eq.16$$

$$u_{cell}(i, P, T) = u_{nernst} - Act_{loss} - Ohm_{loss} - Conc_{loss} \quad eq.17$$

Where A, B, i_{corr}, i_{lim} are parameters that are fitted through the experimental data and r is a known value that corresponds to the equivalent protonic and electronic resistances.

Figure 2: Performance of SM1 on the test set, for each target. The values are sorted in ascending order.

Figure 3: Up: Comparison of the Performance of Electrochemical, SVR, and SM2 models on test set.

Thermal model

Before incorporating the thermal model as a constraint in the BO process, it was validated against the experimental data utilized for model training of SM1 and SM2. Fig. 4 illustrates a comparison between Eq. 4, which quantifies the effectively measured heat extraction, and Eq. 3, which provides the theoretical estimation. It is evident that the two equations exhibit a consistent trend and display values within the same order of magnitude, indicating that the thermal model accurately represents the system. The margin of error between the two equations was assessed using RMSE. Its distribution across every operational region (activation, ohmic, concentration) corresponds to the threshold (the ϵ parameter of Eq. 10) to fall within during the BO iteration.

Figure 4: Validation of the thermal model on experimental data. Bayesian Optimization

As illustrated in Fig.6, the polarization curve corresponding to the optimal θ for each operational region reveals that the optimizer identifies a profile that surpasses the highest point from any experimental polarization curve at nearly every current density point. This results in a 5.1 percent improvement over the best experimental polarization curve. The solution set found by the algorithm demonstrates a clear trend for most variables over current density, effectively discovering new solutions that differ from the best experimental results: Fig.6 also illustrates the percentage variation of the solution sets with respect to the best experimental curve. While the optimal conditions identified maximize the stack voltage in a controlled experimental setup, these conditions will inevitably differ when the stack is integrated into a full system that includes components such as a compressor, a passive humidifier, and a hydrogen recirculation loop.

Figure 5: Upper image: a comparison of Operating Conditions θ : Optimized Set θ_{opt} vs $\theta_{cpl-best}$ from experimental data. Lower Image: the optimized CPL (the blue curve) against every point extracted from every experimental CPL.

Conclusions

In this paper, we present a Physics-Constrained Optimization algorithm that integrates Bayesian Optimization, Surrogate Modeling through a GRU architecture, and a thermal model to optimize the operating conditions of a PEM fuel cell under quasi-static load conditions defined by varying current density inputs. Over 500-hour experimental data, we collected information from a bench test operating across a broad spectrum of conditions. The GRU surrogate models were trained using 70% of the dataset, demonstrating high accuracy when evaluated on the remaining data, achieving a MAPE score ranging from 0.76% to 1.2% in predicting various physical parameters at both the inlet and outlet of the fuel cell, as well as its output voltage. The thermal model, employed as a constraint function in the optimization problem, was validated against this experimental data and effectively represented the thermal profile of the fuel cell across multiple power loads. While this validation satisfies the primary objective of the paper—demonstrating the methodology that integrates a physical equation into a black-box optimization, the model could be significantly improved by elaborating more in-depth assumptions related to relative humidity, as well as the effects of dissipated heat and mass flow exchanges between the anode and cathode. The physics-constrained BO process demonstrated efficiency in searching for optimal solutions within feasible regions, surpassing the peak performance recorded during the experiments. The algorithm provided improved solutions for the approach studied: optimization per operational regions (activation, ohmic, or diffusion), with an average voltage increase of 5.1%. The optimal solution set found by the algorithm presented a clear and uniform trend for each parameter as a function of the current density input. To enhance these results, grey-box models [25] could offer broader exploration of regions for optimal points while adhering to the electrochemical principles derived from the analytical components of the equations. Additionally, with greater computational resources, particularly by employing more computationally expensive acquisition functions in the Gaussian Processes—the search for optimal solutions could be enhanced, reducing the likelihood of becoming trapped in local minima. This approach provides static optimization, meaning it identifies the optimal operational region after an experimental campaign. This can guide further investigation into the physical responses of the PEMFC under the suggested regions and enhance the general understanding of the system. However, it cannot provide real-time resolutions to control the operations. Reinforcement learning [26], which operates with a trained black-box model and a reward function that incorporates the theoretical framework of the system, could instead achieve real-time optimal control.

Acknowledgements

This project was funded by the French State in the frame of France 2030 and Relaunch France, and by the European Union - NextGeneration EU.

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Keywords: *EFCF2025, H₂, LowTemp. Fuel Cells & Electrolysers, Physics-Constrained Optimization, Recurrent Neural Networks, Gated Recurrent Units, Bayesian Optimization*

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